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E-mail: nurmatovayoqutxon@gmail.com**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MOTORIC SKILLS OF GIRLS 5-7 YEARS OLD THROUGH THE MEANS OF RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS**DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16193585>

Annotation. This article analyzes the effectiveness of the use of rhythmic gymnastics in the development of motor skills of girls 5-7 years old. During the study, it was observed that children of this age, through adapted methods of rhythmic gymnastics, which are performed with tools such as tape, hoops, balls, ropes, develop their coordination of movement, balance, fine and large motor skills, ability to control the body, as well as general physical activity. Analysis of the results of training with an experimental group showed that rhythmic gymnastics tools are an effective tool in the formation of movement skills. The results of this study make it possible to develop methodological recommendations for coaches, educators and parents working with girls of preschool age.

Keywords: motor skills, rhythmic gymnastics, Movement Coordination, preschool education, physical education, developmental exercises, sports tools, pedagogical impact, age-appropriate activities

Introduction.

The modern preschool system requires new approaches to the physical education of children. Especially in children between the ages of 5-7, the development of movement activity and motor skills is one of the urgent scientific and practical issues. At this age, the organism of children enters the stage of intensive development, and at the same time the most favorable conditions for their movement activity, maintaining balance, coordination, the formation of small and large motor elements occur. Viewed from this point of view, the fact that it is possible to jointly develop the physical and mental state of children through the use of rhythmic gymnastics is one of the scientifically substantiated approaches. Rhythmic gymnastics forms important motor qualities such as aesthetic appearance, lightness and accuracy of movement, control of the body in children through the technique of working with tools, accurate execution of movement, perception of time and space. Especially exercises performed with such tools as tape, hoops, ropes, balls will increase the interest of the child, change the emotional state in a posi-

five way and form a positive attitude towards physical activity. This study aims to analyze the impact and effectiveness of rhythmic gymnastics tools in the formation of motor skills of girls 5-7 years old. specially exercises performed with such tools as tape, hoops, ropes, balls will increase the interest of the child, change the emotional state in a positive way and form a positive attitude towards physical activity. This study aims to analyze the impact and effectiveness of rhythmic gymnastics tools in the formation of motor skills of girls 5-7 years old. The importance of the study is that it provides an opportunity to further enrich physical education classes in preschool educational institutions and introduce interesting and effective methods. The topic also serves to develop practical recommendations for educators, trainers and parents.

Main part.

Rhythmic gymnastics is a complex, but aesthetic and pleasant form of sports, in which work with movement, musical expression and means is harmonized. This sport not only requires physical strength and dexterity, but also forms a high level of coordination ability, skills to be able to aes-

thetically express the sequence of movements, move freely in space and adapt to musical rhythm. Rhythmic gymnastics is a complex, but aesthetic and pleasant form of sports, in which work with movement, musical expression and means is harmonized. This sport not only requires physical strength and dexterity, but also forms a high level of coordination ability, skills to be able to aesthetically express the sequence of movements, move freely in space and adapt to musical rhythm. It is these aspects that make it an important tool for preschool children, in particular, girls aged 5-7 years. Psychophysiologicaly, this age range is the period when the active movement, thinking and emotional development of the child is most active. By forming motor skills at such a stage, the child develops not only physically, but also psychically and socially. Through movement-based games, rhythmic exercises, tasks aimed at maintaining balance, children's experience of movement is enriched, such qualities as spatial orientation, speed and accuracy are improved.

When working with tape, rings, balls, sticks and ropes, which are the tools of rhythmic gymnastics, children's movement accuracy, synchronicity, the ability to perceive directions in space, the technique of starting, continuing and ending movement is formed. Through this, they learn to consciously control their body parts, the speed of their motor and psychomotoric reactions increases. When working with tape, rings, balls, sticks and ropes, which are the tools of rhythmic gymnastics, children's movement accuracy, synchronicity, the ability to perceive directions in space, the technique of starting, continuing and ending movement is formed. Through this, they learn to consciously control their body parts, the speed of their motor and psychomotoric reactions increases. In addition, in the process of adapting movement to music, children develop characteristics such as aesthetic taste, sense of rhythm, sensitivity and inner discipline. The age range of 5-7 years

is the period when the central nervous system, musculoskeletal system and emotional sensitivity of the child develop with activity, and it is during this period that it is necessary to correctly focus the body's movement functions. Rhythmic gymnastics is a universal tool that can effectively satisfy this need.

The organization of pilot work and analysis of results is the most important stage of research work. In this study, an experimental method was used in order to determine the effectiveness of rhythmic gymnastics tools in the development of motor skills of girls 5-7 years old. They were divided into two groups: the experimental group and the control group. In the experimental group, rhythmic gymnastics was processed on the basis of a special training program based on the means, and in the control group, the usual physical education training was continued. The training sessions were held three times a week, each lasting 30-35 minutes, for a total of 10 weeks.

The experimental program included tasks such as spinning and drawing with tape, jumping with a ring and circular movements, catching and shooting with a ball, rhythmic exercises with a rope, balancing with a stick. In each session, the level of active participation, interest and independent performance of children was controlled. Before and at the beginning of the program, all participants were given motor tests. The tests evaluated the movement accuracy, speed, coordination, ability to balance, and reaction time of children. The results obtained showed that the participants of the experimental group achieved significantly higher indicators in the test results than in the control group. In particular, the balance test results improved by 18%, while the coordination test results improved by 23%. This confirms that the chosen methodology is effective and purposeful. In addition, there was a significant increase in interest in training and emotional activity in the experimental group. According to the results of the observation, children were in-

clined to show mutual competition, creative approach and initiative during work with rhythmic gymnastics tools. All these situations indicate that rhythmic gymnastics has a positive effect not only on motor skills, but also on the personal development of children. In the control group, however, no significant results were recorded.

On the basis of the results of the experiment, the pedagogical effectiveness of the training program for children was highly appreciated. An important role in this was played by the variety of tools, the fact that the movements were based on rhythm, and the training was organized in an interesting form. This scientifically based approach is proposed as a solution of novel, practical importance for the preschool education system.

Methodological recommendations and practical significance are important for educators, coaches and parents working with children. A methodological approach based on the means of rhythmic gymnastics is necessary to be appropriate, interesting, consistent and effective for the age of the child. First of all, it is necessary to harmonize the individual and group types of training, take into account the physical fitness, coordination level and interest of each child. Methodological approaches such as organizing classes with musical accompaniment, selecting tools that correspond to children's color and shape sensitivity, and gradually complicating the sequence of movements lead to high efficiency.

Conclusion.

The formation of motor skills through the means of rhythmic gymnastics takes the quality of physical education in preschool educational institutions to a new level. Activities organized on the basis of scientifically based methodologies serve to ensure the comprehensive development of the child and form him as a healthy and active person. Therefore, the introduction of this approach on a large scale, its inclusion in the programs of training educators and its ap-

plication in practice is one of the urgent tasks.

References

1. Yo'ldoshev M.T. Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi, 2018. – 368 b.
2. Ubaydullayev A.M. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni jismoniy rivojlantirish asoslari. – Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2021. – 224 b.
3. Qodirov A.X., Rasulov B.B. Badiiy gimnastikaning nazariy va amaliy asoslari. – Toshkent: Olim, 2019. – 180 b.
4. Shodmonova N.K., Jo'raeva M.A. Maktabgacha ta'lim metodikasi. – Toshkent: Iqbol, 2020. – 280 b.
5. Tursunov B.B. Bolalar sporti va harakat faoliyati psixofiziologiyasi. – Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2017. – 192 b.
6. Karimova N.M. Maktabgacha ta'limda jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etish. – Samarqand: SamDU nashriyoti, 2022. – 160 b.
7. G'ulomova Z.R. Bolalar motorik rivojlanishini badiiy faoliyat asosida shakllantirish. – Buxoro: BuxDU nashriyoti, 2020. – 210 b.
8. Abdullayeva G.I. 5–7 yoshli bolalarning harakat faoliyatini rivojlantirishda sport o'yinlarining o'rni. // Pedagogik izlanishlar jurnali. – 2023. – №4. – B. 45–50.